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Melamine-meltblown nonwoven a high-performance material combining for the first time thermoset Melamine with excellent thermal and acoustic properties.

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Intruduction SmartMELAMINE :

- ❑ Meltblown technology.
- ❑ Modified melamine (*Figure 1*) polymer.

Figure 1: 1,3,5-Triazine-2,4,6-triamine (melamine).

- ❑ Very fine fibers between **1** and **25 μm**:
 - excellent acoustic insulation,
 - excellent thermal insulation,
 - excellent filtration and
 - lightweight.

- ❑ Thermoset and not thermoplastic.
- ❑ Properties:
 - non-burning,
 - high temperature resistance,
 - no thermal related shrinking, melting and dripping,
 - chemical resistant,
 - UV resistant.

Flame Retardency

- ❑ Inherent flame resistance → LOI 32%.
- ❑ Emissions → very low (ÖkoTex 100 Class 1, VDA 275).
- ❑ Heat dimensional stability → non-shrinking, non-melting, non-dripping.
- ❑ Smoke gas → low, non toxic (EN 45545).
- ❑ Maximum use temperature → up to 350°C.
- ❑ Continuous use temperature → up to 240°C.
- ❑ Thermal decomposition → ~400°C.

Polyester FR

smartMELAMINE®

Filtration:

- ❑ Air filtration range of G2 – F9.
- ❑ Hot-gas filtration → filter efficiency increased up to **10x** compared to aramid type filters.
- ❑ Liquid filtration → easily dispersed/used in water/organic solvent (synthetic substitute to glass fibres).

Figure 2: Filter efficiency test of smartMELAMINE (VDI 3926-1).

Lightweight Acoustic Insulation

- Excellent → due to fine fibers

Figure 3 : Tested sound absorption coefficient (α) (DIN EN ISO 10534-2).

Figure 4: VIP

Vacuum Insulation Panels (VIP)

- fine fibres (1 μm) → excellent thermal insulation.
- comparable to insulation performance of inorganic materials (like glass or rock wool).
- Thermal conductivity as a standalone nonwoven is 0,028 W/mK (DIN 52612).
- Thermal conductivity of VIP's with smartMELAMINE® as core material is as low as 0,002 W/mK.

Conclusion

- ❑ Advantages of smartMELAMINE: flame retardancy, thermal resistance, acoustic insulation, thermal insulation, lightweight, low emission, etc.
- ❑ **3D Formable** → different binder can be used.
- ❑ Application: **transportation vehicles** (cars, trains, buses, trucks and aircraft), **protective workwear**, **filtration**, **construction** and **other various industrial applications** (insulation of pipes, core material for VIP's, etc.).

Figure 5: 3D formable fibres.

References

- ❑ V. Nemanič, M. Žumer, New organic fiber-based core material for vacuum thermal insulation, *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 90, 2015, Pages 137-141.
- ❑ K. Varga, M. F. Noisternig, U. J. Griesser, L. Alja and T. Koch "Thermal and sorption study of flame resistant fibers". *Lenzinger Berichte*, Vol. 89, No. 2, pp 50-59, 2011.
- ❑ H. Diem, M. Günther and R. Wagner. "Amino resins." *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*, 2000.

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THANK YOU!!